

Domestic Violence as Correlates of Senior Secondary Schools Students Academic Performance in Sokoto South Senatorial Zone

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ABSTRACT

The paper focused on Domestic Violence as Correlates of Senior Secondary Schools Students Academic Performance in Sokoto South Senatorial Zone, with all the secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone of Sokoto state as population, three hundred and forty six (346) respondents from the total population of senior secondary school two (II) was used as sample of the study, using Research Adviser (2006) table, proportionate sampling and simple random sampling techniques respectively. Secondary school student's domestic violence questionnaire [SSSDVQ] which was designed by the researcher for the research. The instrument was validated by supervisory team and reliability index was obtained at 0.78. Frequency, percentages and Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was used in analyzing data generated in the study. After the analysis, the results indicated that, there are numerous factors contributing to domestic violence among senior secondary school students in Sokoto South Senatorial Zone. Such as intimidation, rape, sexual coercion among others, there is significant relationship between emotional violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone, there is significant relationship between physical violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone and there is significant relationship between sexual violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone. Domestic Violence protection mechanism should be developed and implemented to secondary school students and their teachers by professional guidance counselors in Sokoto State.

Keywords: Domestic Violence, Secondary Schools Students, Academic Performance

INTRODUCTION

School performance in early years encompasses intellectual, social and physical abilities of every individual learner. Development of these abilities in early years has potential to affect future achievements of children's throughout their school period. Unfortunately, the rampant cases of domestic violence in Nigeria and other African countries like Kenya have negatively socialized young children into a society of ridicule, revenge and survival for the fittest (Sambo& Isa, 2016). Domestic violence has become a global and a widespread phenomenon that has affected millions of children lives globally (UNICEF, 2015). According to Miller (2010), when children learning is favorable, they get chances to various educational opportunities and experiences that are of great benefit to social development and positive relationship with peers and adults. Domestic Violence according to the Act on Protection against Domestic Violence (PADV) (2015), is any form of violence against a person, or imminent danger or a threat of violence to that person, by other person with whom that person has been, or is in a domestic

relationship. According to Abuya and Onsomu (2022), in domestic violence households, children are often involved as invisible victims who are exposed to the abuse.

The phenomenon of violence according to Shahana, (2021), Shija, (2017), Sandesh, (2015) Has assumed an international recognition due largely to its adverse effect on the family, society and national life, as well as complex nature in terms of its various forms. Right to life is one of the fundamental human rights, which cannot be achieved successfully without peace. Ideally, it is every Child's dream, irrespective of age and sex to be surrounded by reflective love of his or her parents, teachers and those surrounded by his immediate environments (society), which is pride among his or her peers a love that will radiates his or her parents, teachers as well as neighbor's healthy relationship with each other. Nevertheless, secondary school students seem to constitute the greater percentage of the recipient of the adverse effect of violence. A study conducted by the office of juveniles justice and delinquency prevention in Geneva Switzerland, found that 70% of adolescents live in families with parental conflict, self-reported violent delinquency compared to 49% of adolescents from household without this conflict (Carter, 2017).

While domestic violence has been recognized as one of the most entrenched and pervasive forms of violence in Uganda today, its influence on school going children have yet to receive the same degree of attention (Tony, 2021). This is despite the fact that every year in Uganda thousands of children as well as women suffer physically, psychologically, and sexually as a result of acts of violence against them in the home- in the urban as well as in the peri-urban areas such as Masese in Jinja Municipality. Despite the introduction of (UBE) Free Basic Education about 32% of school aged children in Nigeria especially in Northern Nigeria including Sokoto state children have dropped out of school (MOEST, 2015), Children who are victims or witnesses of domestic violence may develop physical, psychological and behavioral problems as a result of physical, verbal, psychological and other forms of violence. This may affect their participation in school as they may go to school when they are too scared to learn and a good number of them may lag behind in class as well as in life due to exposure to domestic violence (Wathen, 2016).

The occurrence of violence in one form or the other permeates our life today, and majority of the perpetrators are youths. Children who grew up in a family or society where there is violence, often become violent themselves and in a bid to curtail the aggressive behavior either by parents or school authority become frustrated and may either leave home or drop out of school, life is no longer secured as these youth serve as instrument of violence in political matters, or hired as assassins; partake in armed robbery, bullying, raping and cultism. (Shinding, 2015). Violence has adverse effects on individual, families, and society in general. The multi-dimensional effects of violent, socially, educationally; psychologically and physiologically; has a case for serious investigation in recent times, such that Carter (2017) recorded that 50% of men who frequently assault their wives also frequently assault their children. He further declared, data from a 1995 Gallup poll of family violence suggested that from 1.5 to 3.3 million children witness parental violence each year globally.

Domestic violence incidences have negatively influenced children's learning. Despite the rights of children to protection against all forms of domestic violence, neglect and abuse there is repeated cycles of domestic violence at home; whereby many young children are exposed to and its effects reflected in school (Uwezo, 2022). Fewer studies have been done on domestic violence on learning, however its impact on academic performance of young children need to be unearth. Based on these fact that, the study therefore sought to examine the domestic violence as correlates of senior secondary school students academic performance in Sokoto-South senatorial District.

Objectives

The objectives of the paper are to find out the following:-

1. Factors contributing to domestic violence in among senior secondary schools students in Sokoto South Senatorial Zone.
2. Emotional violence as correlates of senior secondary schools students' academic performance in Sokoto south senatorial zone.
3. Physical violence as correlates of senior secondary schools student's academic performance in Sokoto south senatorial zone.

4. Sexual violence as correlates of senior secondary schools students' academic performance in Sokoto south senatorial zone.

Research Questions

The research questions are:

1. What are the factors contributing to domestic violence in among senior secondary schools students in Sokoto South Senatorial Zone?
2. What are the relationship between emotional violence and academic performance of senior secondary schools students in Sokoto south senatorial zone?
3. What are the relationship between physical violence and academic performance of senior secondary schools students in Sokoto south senatorial zone?
4. What are the relationship between sexual violence and academic performance of senior secondary schools students in Sokoto south senatorial zone?

Hypotheses

Three null hypotheses were postulated to guide the study, they are:

1. There is no significant relationship between emotional violence and academic performance of senior secondary schools students in Sokoto south senatorial zone.
2. There is no significant relationship between physical violence and academic performance of senior secondary schools students in Sokoto south senatorial zone.
3. There is no significant relationship between sexual violence and academic performance of senior secondary schools students in Sokoto south senatorial zone.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopts a descriptive approach which is correlational in nature, the population consist of about forty-two senior secondary schools with a population size of seven thousand, three hundred and twelve (7,312) students of senior secondary schools, SS two (SS II).The sample of this study consist of the three hundred and forty six (346) respondents from the total population of senior secondary schools, SS two (SS II) in Sokoto south senatorial zone. Using Research Adviser (2006) table, proportionate sampling technique and simple random sampling techniques respectively.

Secondary schools students' domestic violence questionnaire [SSSDVQ] which was designed by the researcher for the research. It comprised of five parts. Part A Descriptive data about the respondents such as sex, age, school, location and school type, part B: with ten items about factors contributing to senior Secondary schools students domestics violence, Part C with five items about senior Secondary schools students emotional violence, Part D with five items about senior Secondary schools students physical violence and Part E with five items about senior Secondary schools students sexual violence. The questionnaires was designed on four modified point's likert (rating) scales of strongly agree (SA), agree (A), disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD). Frequency, percentages and Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was used in analyzing data generated in the study. The instrument was validated by the supervisory team. The reliability of the said instrument was obtained at 0.78.

RESULTS

Research Question: *What are the factors contributing to domestic violence in among senior secondary schools students in Sokoto South Senatorial Zone?*

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage on Factors contributing to domestic violence among senior secondary schools students in Sokoto South Senatorial Zone.

Mobile phones are used to	Yes	No	%	%
1. Intimidation	240	106	69.4%	30.6%
2. Rape	254	92	73.4%	26.6%
3. Early marriage	198	148	57.2%	42.8%
4. Sexual harassment	190	156	54.9%	45.1%
5. Sexual coercion	264	92	76.3%	23.7%
6. Poor parenting	196	150	56.7%	43.4%
7. Drug abuse	195	151	56.4%	43.6%
8. Street begging	200	146	57.8%	42.2%
9. Poor parental attitude	225	121	65.0%	35.0%
10. Street hawking	87	259	25.1%	74.9%

Table 1: Frequency and percentage of the factors contributing to domestic violence among senior secondary schools students in Sokoto South Senatorial Zone, indicated that, intimidation accounted for 240 respondents for yes and 106 respondents for no representing 69.4% for yes and 30.6% for no, rape accounted for 254 respondents for yes and 92 respondents for no representing 73.4% for yes 26.6% for no, early marriage accounted for 198 respondents for yes and 148 respondents for no representing 57.2% and 42.8% respectively, sexual harassment accounted for 190 respondents for yes and 156 respondents for no representing 54.9% for yes and 45.1% for no, others include; sexual coercion accounted for 264 respondents for yes and 92 respondents for no representing 76.3% for yes and 23.7% for no, poor parenting accounted for 196 respondents for yes and 150 respondents for no representing 56.7% for yes and 43.3% for no, drug abuse accounted for 195 respondents for yes and 151 respondents for no representing 56.4% for yes and 43.6% for no, street begging accounted for 200 respondents for yes and 146 respondents for no representing 57.8% for yes and 42.2% for no, poor parental care accounted for 225 respondents for yes and 121 respondents for no representing 65.0% for yes and 35.0% for no and finally street hawking accounted for 87 respondents for yes and 259 respondents for no representing 25.1% for yes and 74.9% for no respectively. This confirmed that there are numerous factors contributing to domestic violence among senior secondary school students in Sokoto South Senatorial Zone.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between emotional violence and academic performance of senior secondary schools students in Sokoto south senatorial zone.

Table 2: Relationship between emotional violence and academic performance

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	r-Cal	p-Value	Decision
EV	346	2.331	.23316	.234	.000	H ₀ Rejected
AP	346	2.131	.23778			

Source: Field Work July February, 2025.

From result of Table 2, of emotional violence and academic performance were positively related and significant, $r(346) = .234, p = .000$. This indicates significant relationship between emotional violence and academic performance because the p -value is less than the .05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between emotional violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between physical violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone.

Table 3: Relationship between physical violence and academic performance

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	r-Cal	p-Value	Decision
PV	346	2.131	.23778	.224	.000	H ₀ Rejected
AP	346	2.331	.23316			

Source: Field Work July, 2025.

From result of Table 3, of physical violence and academic performance were positively related and significant, $r(346) = .224, p = .000$. This indicates significant relationship between physical violence and academic performance because the p -value is less than the .05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between physical violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between sexual violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone.

Table 4: Relationship between sexual violence and academic performance

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	r-Cal	p-Value	Decision
SV	346	2.231	.22316	.214	.000	H ₀ Rejected
AP	346	2.431	.24778			

Source: Field Work July, 2025.

From result of Table 4, relationship between sexual violence and academic performance were positively related and significant, $r(346) = .214, p = .000$. This indicates significant relationship between sexual violence and academic performance because the p -value is less than the .05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between sexual violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone.

After the analysis the following are the summary of the major findings:

1. There are numerous factors contributing to domestic violence among senior secondary school students in Sokoto South Senatorial Zone such as intimidation, rape, sexual coercion among others.
2. There is significant relationship between emotional violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone
3. There is significant relationship between physical violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone
4. There is significant relationship between sexual violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone.

DISCUSSION

Based on the Frequency and Percentage of the factors contributing to domestic violence among senior secondary schools students in Sokoto South Senatorial Zone, indicated that, intimidation accounted for 240 respondents for yes and 106 respondents for no representing 69.4% for yes and 30.6% for no, rape accounted for 254 respondents for yes and 92 respondents for no representing 73.4% for yes 26.6% for no, early marriage accounted for 198 respondents for yes and 148 respondents for no representing 57.2% and 42.8% respectively, sexual harassment accounted for 190 respondents for yes and 156 respondents for no representing 54.9% for yes and 45.1% for no, others include; sexual coercion accounted for 264 respondents for yes and 92 respondents for no representing 76.3% for yes and 23.7% for no, poor

parenting accounted for 196 respondents for yes and 150 respondents for no representing 56.7% for yes and 43.3% for no, drug abuse accounted for 195 respondents for yes and 151 respondents for no representing 56.4% for yes and 43.6% for no, street begging accounted for 200 respondents for yes and 146 respondents for no representing 57.8% for yes and 42.2% for no, poor parental care accounted for 225 respondents for yes and 121 respondents for no representing 65.0% for yes and 35.0% for no and finally street hawking accounted for 87 respondents for yes and 259 respondents for no representing 25.1% for yes and 74.9% for no respectively. This confirmed that there are numerous factors contributing to domestic violence among senior secondary schools students in Sokoto South Senatorial Zone.

These findings also agree with previously existing studies for example; Imam (2021) observed that; in both industrial and developing countries, sexual coercion usually takes the children or place against the children or adolescents' wishes. Others include rape, assault, and killing of women is also a common feature of war and ethnic conflicts, whether in the north-west, north-east as well as north-central part of Nigeria. Others are; Hindu Muslim conflict in India, the Arab African fighting in Dafur, a region in the Sudan in Africa, or the genocide in Rwanda. Military forces use sexualized forms of violence to establish control over subordinated, populations, include those who are captured. Colonialism, created through conquest, is maintained through violence, including rape and battery of subordinate group women dominant-group men. Men of the conquering group can typically abuse or killed subordinate women with impunity.

Based on the analysis of hypothesis one which states that, there is no significant relationship between emotional violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone. From result of Table 2, of emotional violence and academic performance were positively related and significant, $t(346) = .234, p = .000$. This indicates significant relationship between emotional violence and academic performance because the p -value is less than the .05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between emotional violence and academic performance of senior secondary schools students in Sokoto south senatorial zone.

This finding also agrees with previously existing studies for example; UNICEF (2017) stated that, Violence can have severe implications for children development. It can affect children's health, their ability to learn or even their willingness to go school. It can lead children to run away from home, exposing them to further danger. Violence also Destroy child's self-confidence and esteem and undermines their ability to grow into well-adjusted adults. Children subjected to violence are prone to depression and suicide in later life. In most cases, violence Led to injury and death. According to UN secretary general's survey on violence against children, the consequences of violence can be devastating. These include, brain injuries, bruises and fractures, poor interpersonal relationship and communication, learning problem, emotional/psychological problems like anxiety, depression, aggression or attempted suicide, use of drugs, sexual indulgence and health problems such as HIV/AIDS and sexually transmitted infections (STDs). Above all, most of the impacts can result in early death while those who survive lives with physical and emotional scars.

Hypothesis two which states that, there is no significant relationship between physical violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone. From result of Table 3, of physical violence and academic performance were positively related and significant, $t(346) = .224, p = .000$. This indicates significant relationship between physical violence and academic performance because the p -value is less than the .05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between physical violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone. These findings also agree with previously existing studies for example; Ndagi (2020) confirms that, truancy and absenteeism could be traced to the circumstances at home. These include poor physical home conditions, poor parent-child relationship characterized by hostility, lack of attention and under-involvement on the child's welfare, overly harsh and authoritarian methods of discipline and high degree of family conflict and disorganization.

Also Wife and children battering have a multiplier effect on the cycle of violent in the society. Levine in Ndagi (2020) observed that children living in violence homes are themselves more likely to become agents of violence as they grow up. Also Mohammed (2015) asserts that such children naturally see violence as an instrument of inter-group relations. To buttress this, he also opines that if a child is always being punished through infliction of pain for every minor offence, such a child soon becomes resistant even to dangerous battering and gladly participates in street fight. Parents serve as models whose behavior children imitate. If the parents are always demonstrating aggressive or violent behaviour either directly towards the child or stands as a witness, consciously or unconsciously the child learns the act of being aggressive or violent.

With regard to hypothesis three which states that, there is no significant relationship between sexual violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone. From result of Table 4, of sexual violence and academic performance were positively related and significant, $t(346) = .214, p = .000$. This indicates significant relationship between sexual violence and academic performance because the p -value is less than the .05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between sexual violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone. This finding also agrees with previously existing studies for example; Ogundipe and Obinna (2017) observed that, Sexual violence and rape of children have appears to be spiraling, inexcusably fuelled by armed conflicts, extreme poverty and HIV/AIDS. In Nigeria, sexual abuse of children often takes place behind closed doors and is unreported and undetected. UNICEF Nigeria representative AyalewAbai said that. "Figures do not exist, but it does not mean that children are not abused. There are thousands of children leaving on the streets of Lagos and other major cities, neglected by their parents or abandoned, exposed to so many hazards and threats. However, there is lack of information on the status of violence against children in schools in Nigeria. It is common for children to keep quiet about episodes of victimization due to shame, embarrassment and fear of escalated violence.

CONCLUSION

Conclusion drawn from the study confirmed that; there are numerous factors contributing to domestic violence among senior secondary schools students in Sokoto South Senatorial Zone such as intimidation, rape, sexual coercion among others, this shows that domestic violence is as a results of human factors within our society and if not curtail, it will cause serious harm not only to the victims but to the entire generation. There is significant relationship between emotional violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone, domestic violence lead to emotional disturbance and inadequacies as well as poor feelings especially with regard to school and academic activities.

There is significant relationship between physical violence and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone, victims of physical violence i.e excessive use of energy among and between students affect their academic activities and school related works such attending lessons, writing notes, assignments and tutorials. There is significant impact of sexual violence on the academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone victims of sexual violence are usually demoralized and isolate themselves from larger society not only in the school, leading to poor performance and decline in the entire school related activities. Finally, there is significant relationship between child abuse and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto south senatorial zone. Children learn faster both right and wrong behavior, when they are exposed to abuses they may end of retaliating and even go beyond the societal experiences and may likely drop out from the school.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Domestic Violence protection mechanism should be developed and implemented to secondary schools students and their teachers by professional guidance counsellors in Sokoto state.
2. There is need for the inclusion of domestic violence defense mechanism in the orientation program of newly admitted senior secondary schools students in Sokoto state.
3. State Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education in the state should partner with professional and academic associations and clubs in the fight against domestic violence among secondary schools students in the Sokoto state.
4. Laws established and or enacted to fight and punished domestic violence offenders should be adhered to strictly so as to curb the menace.

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